

Analysis of the Integration of Electric Vehicle Charging Stations to the Electricity Network in Residential Areas

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Abstract

Because of economic and environmental considerations, the number of electric cars has reached a significant value across the board in every region of the world. Because of the growing number of electric vehicles connecting to the distribution grid, it is imperative that research be conducted on the effects that EVs have on the planning and operation of distribution networks. Despite the fact that various research has been conducted on the subject of the effects of electric vehicles (EVs) on distribution grids, one particular study concerning the English distribution network does not provide sufficient evidence. Because the infrastructure required to support the widespread use of environmentally friendly electric cars is not yet in place, it is reasonable to anticipate that the process of charging automobiles will be subject to certain challenges. Differences between the electricity that is installed and the power that is required in residential constructions. The effects of electric vehicles on low-voltage distribution networks in residential areas of Turkey are the primary subject of this study. In the course of this research, an integrated distribution network with actual user data and the consumption characteristics of the revealed scenarios was built and investigated using charging stations for electric vehicles. It has become possible to make widespread use of electric vehicle charging facilities. In order to generate and report network results based on transformer overloads, cable overloads, and grid loss, a technique is being developed right now. The person responsible for making the decision will find this process helpful in determining the investments on the distribution

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network and the corresponding time period. That will lead to the development of the planning mechanism of distribution firms, which will result in those companies submitting investment plans to the regulatory body that are more practical and accurate.

Keywords: *Electric Vehicle, Distribution System, Charging Station, Smart Grids.*

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1. Introduction

The rise in environmental and air pollution that has occurred in recent years has started to produce substantial impacts that are permanent. In order to lessen the severity of these impacts, people in a variety of different fields are sounding very grave warnings that the usage of fossil fuels should be cut back or perhaps abandoned entirely. The rise in atmospheric pollution is to blame for the abnormally high levels of greenhouse gas emissions that are causing difficulties associated with global warming and other aspects of climate change.

According to the most recent data that has been compiled, fossil fuels provide 83% of the world's demand for electrical energy (BP Statical, 2021). With the advent of the industrial revolution, people's need for fossil fuels began to rise for the very first time in human history. The level of CO₂ in the atmosphere may be used to evaluate whether or not there has been a rise in the consumption of fossil fuels. Before the beginning of the industrial revolution, the rate of carbon emissions that was measured and found to be 280 ppm in 2013 was found to be 400 ppm in 2013. According to the findings of these measures, there has been an increase in carbon emissions of around 43 percent during a time span of approximately 263 years (Kibert, 2016).

In 2019, the European Union Commission worked on developing the protocol for the Green Agreement in order to reduce the effects of carbon emissions and the amount of carbon emissions that are produced. In this protocol, regulations and regulations that will decrease the impacts have been filed for approval. These laws and regulations will lessen the effects. According to the European Green Deal (2019), the goal is to cut carbon emissions by 55% by the year 2030. Many different industries will be considerably impacted as a result of the carbon emission restrictions that are stipulated in the laws and regulations that are included in this protocol.

The transportation industry is at the top of the list of industries that will be affected as a result of the limitation of carbon emissions since electric cars are gradually replacing vehicles that run on fossil fuels. Because of this, a growth in the number of electric cars will have an effect not only on the transportation sector but also on the energy sector, as the infrastructure of the power system would need to be upgraded. When the study is analyzed, it is anticipated that the value of the carbon emission generated by cars powered by fossil fuels would have reached zero by the year 2035. 2019), the Commission. It is required to make investments in infrastructure in order to launch electric car models both in the globe and in our nation and to satisfy the energy demand that will develop in order to achieve success within the scope of this goal. This is necessary in order to achieve success within the context of this aim. In order to make the switch to electric cars in a manner that is environmentally friendly, it is necessary to do in-depth research on the installation of charging stations, layout analysis, the impact these stations have on power networks, and the development of optimum charging models.

If we look at the number of electric vehicles in Europe, we can see that the sales rates of electric vehicles have climbed by around 70 percent, and the number of electric vehicles in Europe is expected to reach 2.3 million in 2021. Rechargeable hybrid car types make up around fifty percent of all electric vehicles. The pace of sales of electric vehicles in 2019 was approximately 25% greater than the rate expected in 2021. The number of sales of electric vehicles in 2020 is anticipated to be significantly higher than that of 2021. 2019 and 2020 sales projections for the number of electric vehicles.

Because of the newly implemented regulations on carbon emission (International Energy Agency, 2022). The number of electric vehicles in our nation is growing, and the market share of electric vehicles is growing incrementally thanks to the investments and incentives that have been made. There was a total of 5004 electric cars sold in Turkey by the end of 2022 (Energy Atlas, 2022). This represents a 237% increase in the number of electric vehicles sold in Turkey in 2021 compared to the number of electric vehicles sold in 2020. According to Arnold and Provan (2019), the local electric car manufacturing capacity will have an effect on the already existing industrial base, despite the fact that the demand increase is not large.

It is a given that the electric vehicles manufactured in our nation by the Automobile Development Group of Turkey will begin to be offered for sale in 2023, and it is also evident that the number of electric vehicles will continue to rise on a daily basis in light of the growing global population. The increased demand for power that will be created by charging stations will have an effect on the infrastructures of firms that distribute electricity since the number of charging stations will need to expand in order to charge the batteries of electric cars. Today, with the development of common living spaces, on the other hand, with the growth in urbanization and population, large-capacity parking lots will become ubiquitous. Today, with the intensification of collective living spaces, on the other hand, with the increase in urbanization and population. The interference of electric automobiles in the aforementioned locations will cause the distribution system to be negatively affected by raising the quantity of energy per unit area required from the electricity grid. This will result in an increase in the amount of energy consumed by electric vehicles.

2. Source Research

The use of fossil fuels and the impacts on the environment have expedited the development of electric cars, according to the literature on the examination of the effect that charging stations for electric vehicles have on the power distribution network in residential areas. This is because of the environmental implications. However, charging electric vehicles as a variable resource presents a number of challenges and can be included into the grid in the form of a large-scale distributed generating system. Since this makes it more difficult for the distribution system to run reliably, it has been decided to use the two-order cone flexibility approach, in which non-linear portions must be

linearized, in order to enhance the level of reliability (Xue et al., 2022). This has been chosen in order to increase the level of dependability. Based on the additional costs caused by the effects such as electricity distribution network reliability, voltage drop, and power loss in charging electric vehicles, it was suggested in a different study that electric vehicles should be in an optimal position while charging. Additionally, it was attempted to be optimized by adopting the evolutionary calculation method (Ahmaad et al., 2022). In a study that takes into account the seasonal effects of EVs on the daily load curve, it has been reported that, contrary to what is thought, EVs cause more difficulties in the integration of the grid in the summer months than in the winter months, and create more difficulties at the time of charging (Nafi et al., 2022). This is because EVs take longer to charge in the summer than they do in the winter months. When a large number of electric vehicles are charged at the same time, it is inevitable that the rapid increase in the loading rates of charging stations and distribution transformers will cause burnout or tripping, increasing voltage drops and causing harmonics (Ucer et al., 2018). This is because of the rapid increase in the loading rates caused by the rapid increase in the number of electric vehicles being charged at the same time. The increased load demand that will occur as a result of the charging of electric cars will have an impact on the equilibrium of the electric power system. Because of this, the fact that the electrical grid line operates in a holistic manner is not something that should be neglected (Das et al., 2020).

It has been suggested that the electricity grid system may be controlled in a flexible manner, and load transfers can be undertaken, in order to lessen the impact that charging stations have on the energy grid system (Liu et al., 2021). According to Araujo et al.'s research from 2021, in order to grow the number of electric vehicles and remain competitive, manufacturers will need to find solutions to the issues that arise during the vehicles' integration with the distribution grid.

The operator of the distribution system should undertake analyses in order to preserve system assets and minimize any potential consequences that might be caused by uncoordinated EV charging. In particular, calculations such as the demand meeting capacity and voltage drop of the system are essential for the assets of the electrical system to operate without going beyond the parameters that have been stated. Through the development of analyses and problem-oriented tactics, a system's operation may be made to run more smoothly. In addition, research that has been published demonstrates that optimization studies conducted over charging stations play a significant part in the safer, more stable, and more cost-effective functioning of the distribution system (Wang et al., 2019). This research was conducted by Wang et al.

When we look at a number of studies that have been done in this area, we find that both the planning and operational viewpoints that control the process of charging and discharging electric cars have been investigated. According to the findings of a study conducted by Diaz et al. (2018), it has been hypothesized that an electric car may be charged by modifying the amount of energy that is

supplied to the electric vehicle charging station in the electric power system management of electric vehicles. This concept is referred to as flexible load. Research was conducted to assess the impact that charging stations for electric vehicles have on the lifespan of distribution transformers that are part of the system that distributes power. The lifetime of the distribution transformer as well as the overall harmonicity of the current drawn from the charging station for electric vehicles are also topics that are addressed in this particular study. A quadratic computation is used to construct the formulation of the distortion. complete harmonic resonance in a separate analytical study aimed at lowering the distortion value, the use of an LCL filter was investigated, and the researchers found that the harmonic level dropped by thirty percent as a result (Güven and Akbaşak, 2021). According to the findings of another piece of research, conventional distribution transformers should be abandoned in favor of more modern alternatives that include increased levels of insulation. When charging, the increased demand for electric vehicles drives up the occupancy rate of distribution transformers. According to Qian et al.'s research from 2021, the option was made for this reason since it was revealed that the rise in thermal temperatures that resulted from overloading the distribution transformer was the basis for this choice.

- In this study, the impacts of the charging stations that are intended to be created in the mass housing region on the power system were evaluated using real data collected from the distribution system operator. The findings of this study may be found in the following paragraphs.

- Tables and diagrams illustrate the changes that may occur on the network assets of various areas in the analyzed mass housing region where a charging station infrastructure may be constructed. These points are considered potential locations for the installation of charging stations.

- After the data were processed according to the technical data table obtained from the manufacturer of the electric vehicle charging station, analyses were carried out in the light of the determined situations, and future recommendations were presented from the perspective of the system operator (Vestel Project Media, 2023).

- Economic studies were conducted by taking into consideration the developing scenarios and making estimations for the number of electric cars that would be on the roads in Turkey in the years 2025 and 2030.

Chapter 3 provides an explanation of the simulation of the power distribution system that was utilized for the research, as well as the results of the tests and analyses that were carried out in the Matlab&Simulink environment. Chapter 4 contains an in-depth analysis as well as a presentation of the overall results that were collected.

3. Material and Method

This research looked at an energy distribution system that had a ring network topology with mainly balanced loads. This configuration can be seen in areas where there are concentrations of mass housing developments. There is a decrease in the number of subscribers who are impacted by the failure, which is one of the conveniences that the ring network structure offers to the electrical distribution system. Additionally, there is a reduction in the amount of time required to resolve issues. Following the identification of the site of failure, the defective network inventory is isolated, and the subscribers are then supplied with data from a different location in line with the maneuver instructions. Distribution system operators are required to have supply continuity performance indicators in order to comply with the legislation and implementation principles that have been established by the Energy Market Regulatory Authority (EMRA). The average downtime (SAIDI) is one of these performance indicators, while the average outage frequency (SAIFI) is the other (EMRA Quality Factor, 2021). Both of these indicators are defined as the average.

Figure 1 depicts the single-line model of the 34.5 kV voltage level that was simulated for the relevant region of the electrical distribution system in this study. Clean energy and unclean energy are the two categories of energy that are used in the context of the power distribution network. The TEA downloader is the feeder for environmentally friendly energy. Also known as feeder. After it is transferred from the TEA downloader to the distribution center, the dirty energy flows through the feeders that connect the rings that have been created around the distribution center. After each ring feeder that is utilized to convey electrical energy from the distribution center to the substations on the ring line, the energy that is being sent becomes contaminated. Because of the loads that are placed on the transformer centers through which the energy flows, the quality of the energy is degraded, which is why the term pollution is included in the definition of degraded energy here. Voltage drops and relative harmonic levels are kept to a minimum in clean energy production. The mass housing area, which is the first distribution point visited by the feeder coming from TEA downloader, has been selected as the location at which the measurements are to be conducted in order to ensure that the results obtained are as exact as possible.

Figure 1. Basic Simulation of The Electrical Distribution Network in The Simulink Software

The comprehensive simulation circuit that was designed using the Simulink program looks like the one in Figure 2. The power transformer, the power cable that will be utilized, the distribution transformer, the variable load (the amount of power that will be consumed by the residential area), three charging stations for electric vehicles, and measuring blocks have all been built in this area.

Figure 2. Detailed Simulation of the Electricity Distribution Network in the Simulink Program of the Selected Study Area (Detailed Simulation of The Electrical Distribution Network in The Simulink Software)

In order to discuss the creation of the simulation, it should be noted that the Tepe (H11) feeder from TEA Buyukbakkalkoy downstream supplies the 7450 as well as the other transformers in that ring. The Distribution Center (DM) at 7450 is the first location that the feeder visits. It then travels to many additional transformer centers from here. It has been found, as a consequence of the measurements that were performed, that the distribution transformer only has a 5% occupancy rate, despite the fact that the transformer has a power rating of 1600 kVA. In addition to this, 400 kVA were added to the simulation in order to further evaluate the behavior of the system, to examine the variations in the system when the electric car is introduced, and to supply the number of electric vehicles to be as near as possible to the real ones. This particular distribution transformer is of the hermetic kind and has a Dyn11 connection group. It has a load loss of 14310 W, a no-load loss of 2033 W, a % uk value of 2.76, a 6-stage ONAN cooling class (it is presently available in the 4th stage), a primary current of 27.9 A, and a secondary current of 2309.4 A. It has a load loss of 14310 W, a no-load loss of 2033 W, and a % uk value of 2.76. (The voltage at the first step is 28500, while the voltage at the final stage is 36000) For high voltage applications, 3x240 Cu or 3x400 Al cable is typically utilized. Because the cables that are used to connect the 7450 DM to the outside world are 3x400 Al cables, the impedance values per kilometer of the 3x400 Al cable are measured. The power control device (GKC) that is linked to the LV side of the transformer and the current, voltage, and other measurements that are collected by going to the DM make up the domestic load values. It is a

modeling of the load that was developed with the results of measurements.

The region that is the subject of the study, as well as the electrical values of the relevant distribution firm that is responsible for the distribution of power on the Anatolian side of Istanbul. The relevant distribution company's SCADA center and GKC (G. Erten, personal contact 05 January 2023). The measurement results that were obtained every 10 minutes are included in the data that was received from the SCADA center and the GKC.

According to the load data from GKC and DM, the DM fed site in the specified region is laid up in the same manner as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Simulation Of Load Profile in The Simulink Software

On the LV side of the distribution transformer, the output of the 7450DM displays the total amount of power that has been transmitted over the course of one day. It can be observed that the hours with the highest demand are between the hours of 20 and 21, and the hours with the lowest demand are between the hours of 3 and 4. It has been noted that the demand for energy begins to rise around seven in the morning and reaches its peak in the late afternoon. We may make the conclusion that roughly 260 kW of energy is pulled when the measurement is made from the highest position, whereas approximately 120 kW is drawn when the measurement is taken from the lowest point.

The implications of installing charging stations for electric vehicles in areas with dense populations of people were investigated in this scholarly research. All of the data that was used and the analyses that were carried out were done so in light of actual data. Table 1 provides an overview of the various technological aspects of the charging station for electric vehicles that was utilized (Vestel Project Partner, 2023).

Table 1. Electrical Characteristic of Electric Vehicle Charging Station (Electrical Characteristics of The Electrical vehicle Charging Station)

MODEL	EVCO2-11
Strength	11 kW
Income	400V AC, 3 Phase
Flow	1x16A
Socket Type	TIP2EU
Dimension	647X180X184
Weight	11.2 Kg
HR Class	IK10

In this study, an investigation into the charging states was carried out by utilizing the electric vehicle charging station blocks that were established in the simulation circuit. This allowed for an accurate determination of the charging status. These instances were constructed with the power rates that are utilized in Turkey in mind. Within the residential customer group that makes up the entirety of the Turkish electrical system, there are a total of two different subscription kinds. Add the single as a subscription type to your mix.

are types that are denoted as concurrent as well as dual-timers. There are three different prices for the double time kind of tariff. Day, peak, and night pricing are all included in this table (EMRA Tariff Tables Based on Electricity Bills, 1 January 2023). It may be broken down into four primary categories, which are as follows: load distribution based solely on daytime tariffs; load distribution that takes into account both daytime and peak rates; load distribution that takes into account the consumption patterns of persons who commute to work on a daily basis; and load distribution that takes into account just daytime tariffs. These scenarios are the same as those in Table 2.

Table 2. Situations Of the EV Charging station)

STATUS SEQUENC E	NUMBER OF CHARGED VEHICLES	CHARGING PERCENTA GES	CHARGING TIME
one	5	16.67%	02:00-06:00
one	5	33.33%	05:00-08:00
one	5	0%	19:00-00:00
2	7	0%	08:00-13:00
2	5	0%	12:00-17:00
2	3	33.33%	11:00-14:00
3	10	0%	00:00-05:00
3	7	0%	12:00-17:00
3	6	16.67%	19:00-23:00
4	5	50%	06:00-08:00
4	7	0%	13:00-18:00
4	4	16.67%	20:00-00:00

In this setup, the TEA transformer serves as the voltage source. On the Anatolian side of TEA, the input voltages of step-down centers may range anywhere from 154 kV to 380 kV, while the output voltages can range anywhere from 10 kV to 34.5 kV voltage levels. This research makes use of a

power transformer in TEA that has a step-down configuration and operates at a voltage level of 154/34.5 kV. Figure 4 depicts the sub-block of the voltage source that was used to mimic the voltage in the system depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 4. Simulation of Voltage Subblock in Simulink Program (Simulation of The Voltage subblock In the Simulink Software)

The amount of energy that is used in residential settings might shift on an hourly or even minutely basis. GKC took readings every 10 minutes from 7450 DM to determine the variable load that was present in the system depicted in Figure 1. The data that were collected as a consequence of these measurements were processed into the sub-block, and a variable load was produced as a result of this processing, as can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 5. Simulation of Variable Load Subblock in Simulink Program (Simulation of The Variable Load subblock In the Simulink Software)

Calculations and processing are performed on the currents obtained from the charging stations for electric vehicles when the electric vehicles are being charged. These calculations and processing are included into the electric vehicle sub-block shown in Figure 6 to create the electric vehicle block.

Figure 6. Simulation of Electric Vehicle Subblock in Simulink Program (Simulation of The Electrical vehicle subblock In the Simulink Software)

4. Experimental Results

When compared to the real active power values that were measured, the active power values that were derived as a consequence of the simulation had a margin of error that is 9% higher. This margin of error exists due to several factors, including the fact that the elements utilized in the simulation are ideal, the fact that the simulation does not take into consideration reactive powers, and the fact that the cables that were used in the simulation were really spliced from multiple locations, as well as other factors, such as the age of the cable. There was a distinction for the aforementioned factors. Figure 7 presents a graph of the active power used by the variable load in the system and the actual power pulled from the transformer of the 7450 DM in the absence of electric car charging facilities. This graph may be found below. This picture does not include any reference to electric vehicles in any way. Only the comparison of the data generated by the simulation with the actual data collected from the system will be covered in this section.

Figure 7. LV Bus Active Power Analysis of the LV Bus Before and After Electric Vehicle Incorporation before Andeanafter EVs Connection)

It has been discovered that a maximum occupancy rate of 70% may be reached in the transformers that are utilized in the electrical distribution system. When it reaches or goes over 70%, the transformer's output power is raised. In the event that the power of the transformer is 1600 kVA, a new transformer will be connected to the system. As a result of our research, we found that the transformer has an average occupancy rate of 48% when electric cars are not utilized in the residential area at all. This rate is significantly lower than the typical rate of 100%. The most of the time, it is in the 48% band, even though it can be seen that it somewhat reaches the 70% band during the nighttime. In scenario 1, the same number of electric cars are connected to the system in accordance with the tariffs that are in place for the electrical system. On the network side, problems caused by electric vehicles connected between 02:00 and 08:00 are not an issue. Between the hours of 5:00 and 6:00, there is an overlap of cars linked to the charging stations of two different locations. Due to the fact that energy usage is at its lowest during these hours, the grid will not be pressed. As can be observed, the load rate of the transformer is within the band that corresponds to 50% of its maximum capacity during those hours. The fact that the cars that are going to be connected between 19:00 and 0:00 will be linked in the band with the greatest consumption indicates that the occupancy rate has climbed to the 77% band, which indicates that it has passed the band with a threshold of 70%. In Case 2, the daytime tariff accommodates a variety of various numbers of electric cars that are linked to the system. It has been observed that seven electric cars connected to the transformer between the hours of 8:00 and 13:00 are responsible for the increase in the occupancy rate to 70%. It is obvious that 5 vehicles connected between 12.00 and 17.00 combined with the energy consumption at that time and kept the occupancy rate at 65%, but the occupancy rate exceeded 75% in the hours when the overlap situation in the previous time zone with the 3 vehicles connected in the 11.00 and 14.00 time zones. These hours occurred in the previous time zone. In Case 3, there is a disparity between the daytime

and peak connection counts for the number of electric cars that are powered by the system. It has been noted that the occupancy rate of the transformer approaches 70% during the noontime hours when the energy consumption intensity of humans is high due to the connection of seven automobiles between the hours of 12:00 and 17:00. It has been observed that the connection of six car converters between the hours of 19.00 and 23.00 brings the occupancy rate closer to the 80% band. It has been noted that the occupancy rate of 10 cars linked between 00:00 and 05:00 at night has greatly increased and has been hovering around the 70% mark. In Case 4, a varying number of electric cars were plugged into the grid throughout the busiest hours of the afternoon and for brief durations later that evening. It has been seen that the occupancy rate of the transformer has climbed to 45% with a total of 5 cars being connected between the hours of 06:00 and 08:00. It can be observed that connecting 7 car converters between the hours of 13.00 and 18.00 brings the occupancy rate closer to the band that contains 65% of the available spaces. It has been seen that the occupancy rate of the four linked cars between the hours of 20:00 and 00:00 at night has grown and has been hovering around the 75% range. Figure 8 presents the graph that depicts the loading ratios of the transformers in accordance with the scenarios that were calculated.

Figure 8. Comparison of Transformer Power Occupancy Rate by Situation(Comparison Ugh loading Ratio of The Transformer power according to The Situations)

It is clear from looking at the graph in Figure 8 that the energy distribution network is the weakest link in the chain. This is because losses are calculated during the process of carrying power from the stage of generation to the stage when it is used by consumers. The use of unlawful energy, faults made during wiring, and the inefficiency of transformers are all examples of things that might contribute to losses in the power distribution network. The line losses that occur as a result of the consequences of various scenarios, as well as those that occur when the electric cars are not connected, are investigated throughout all three stages in the simulation research. Table 3 displays the line losses that occurred during all three periods of operation.

Table 3. Line Losses by Conditions (Line Losses according to The Situations)

	REAL SYSTEM LOSS (W)	STATUS 1 (W)	CASE 2 (W)	CASE 3 (W)	CASE 4 (W)
PHASE A	5.302	6,986	5,825	6.11	6,783
PHASE B	4.842	6.443	5.331	5,596	6.249
PHASE C	5,205	6,871	5.721	6.017	6.67

The results described above were acquired by conducting an electrical analysis. The evaluation of these data from an economic standpoint is also very significant for engineering. EMRA is in charge of establishing the pricing per unit of power in our nation. The unit pricing is broken down into a variety of categories such as medium voltage, low voltage, transmission system user, and so on. According to the EMRA Tariff Tables Based on Electricity Bills published on January 1, 2023, each category is further subdivided into subcategories within itself. The area that we are looking at falls under the categories of low-voltage monomial and residential power consumption (less than 8 kWh per day), thus we are evaluating it. A comparison was made between the uninominal and multinomial costs of energy, the total and per-vehicle costs were computed, and the findings are described in Table 4.

When looking at the table of costs associated with charging electric vehicles, it is vital to look at the cost line per vehicle because the expenses associated with charging vary based on the circumstances. The reason for this is that the charging stations for electric vehicles need to be supplied with electricity from the common area, and the number of vehicles charging at any one moment might vary. When seen through the lens of economics, the first scenario emerges as the one that produces the most economically advantageous conclusion. In this instance, five cars were issued citations between the hours of 02:00 and 06:00, five vehicles were issued citations between 05:00 and 08:00, and five vehicles were issued citations between 19:00 and 00:00. If we review the economic analysis of this circumstance, we find that 10% of the expenses occur in the T1 period, 40% in the T2 timeframe, and 50% in the T3 timeframe. This is the case because 10%, 40%, and 50% of the costs occur in the T1, T2, and T3 timeframes, respectively. The second scenario was the one that was the least profitable. In this particular instance, the process of charging 15 automobiles was investigated. Of them, 7 were charged between 08:00 and 13:00, 5 were charged between 12:00 and 17:00, and 3 were charged between 11:00 and 14:00. To provide a concise summary of the findings of the economic analysis performed on this scenario, it has been determined that the T1 time frame is the

only one in which all of the expenses would be incurred. When compared to the first example, the energy cost of using a single term subscription is 23% cheaper; when compared to the second case, it is 34% lower; when compared to the third case, it is 30% lower; and when compared to the fourth case, it is 38% lower when compared to using a multi-term subscription.

Table 4. Comparison Of the Cost of Consumed Energy according to charging Situations)

	Unit Price (kWh / krş)	Actual Status Price (TL)	Case 1 Price (TL)	Case 2 Price (TL)	Case 3 Price (TL)	Case 4 Price (TL)
T ₁	236,1424	7.4810	128.7921	1622,5911	811,2908	938,7794
T ₂	345,0771	6.9568	508,0915	0.0000	846,7847	519.3686
T ₃	149,0277	0.8584	613,5813	0.0000	731,4280	121.8987
Total	-	15.2961	1250,4649	1622,5911	2389,5035	1580.0467
Cost Per Vehicle	-	-	83.3643	108,1727	103,8915	98.7529
Single Term	156,6703	9,0242	961,1770	1076,5192	1691,6476	986,7910
Cost Per Vehicle	-	-	64.0785	71.7679	73,5499	61.6744

5. Results And Suggestions

People's awareness of the environment has grown in tandem with the advancement of technology, and as a result, more and more of them are gravitating toward electric automobiles rather than traditional ones. The need for charging stations for electric cars is fast growing as a result of the growing number of electric vehicles on the road. The number of charging stations for electric vehicles is expected to progressively expand so that they can fulfill the demand for charging. At the same level as the power is distributed, charging stations will be linked in the city. This need is expected to expand even more as a result of the addition of charging stations for electric vehicles to the electrical grid in metropolitan areas, which already have a high demand for energy. When an electric car is linked to the grid, it has been shown that the transformer load rate increases to more than 70 percent. This finding is in accordance with the growing demand for electricity. In this scenario, the power output of the already-installed 400 kVA transformer ought to be raised to 630 kVA, and the latter figure ought to be chosen. However, because investments in network infrastructure are often made for a period of 15 years, a transformer with a capacity of 1600 kVA should be constructed. This is necessary when taking into account the fact that the number of electric cars on the road will continue to rise over the next 15 years and that urbanization will spread over the region. In this study, the expenditures incurred by the electric cars that were a part of the system were broken down and studied according to single-term subscriptions as well as multi-term memberships. It looks to be at capacity. When the

needs that will occur in 2025 and 2030 within the framework of Turkey's plan for the development of electric vehicles are examined, it is predicted that there will be 270 thousand electric vehicles in 2025 and that there will be 1 million 600 thousand electric vehicles in 2030 (TC Ministry of Industry and Technology, 2022). Taking into account the technical features of the electric vehicle charging station that was employed in this simulation, it is recommended that 151 thousand 515 electric car charging stations be erected by the year 2030 in order to satisfy the demand that has been forecasted for 25 thousand 568 electric vehicle charging stations by the year 2025. Only

When the energy demands to be generated for the electric car charging supply are computed, the demand for energy in 2025 is calculated to be 13,500 MWh, and the need for energy in 2030 is predicted to be 80,000 MWh. During the course of this simulation research, it was taken into consideration that the infrastructure preparations for the power distribution system should get underway as soon as possible. This was done with the intention of satisfying the requirements that were generated as a result of the electrical analyses, cost analyses, and forecasts of the Turkish development plan.

Research And Broadcasting Ethics Statement

Based on the findings of the research, in addition, ethical standards for broadcasting have been met.

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